

Host plant range of leafhopper *Cicadulina bipunctata* (Melichar)

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Cicadulina bipunctata is commonly found in habitats associated with rice, and it can vector rice diseases such as rice leaf gall and stripe virus. Its development was studied on 33 common ricefield plants belonging to families Poaceae (24), Cyperaceae (6), and Leguminosae (3). Each species was established in 20-cm-diam clay pots. Five pairs of newly emerged adults, from a colony maintained on rice in a greenhouse, were released onto 25- to 30-d-old individual host plants enclosed in 10- × 72-cm cylindrical mylar cages with side and top nylon mesh (1 mm²) vents. Insects were allowed to oviposit for 5 d. Nymphal survival and fecundity were used to determine host suitability. Each caged plant served as a treatment. The no-choice experiment was replicated 10 times in a randomized complete block design in a greenhouse where temperature averaged 27.6 ± 1.5°C and relative humidity, 66.8 ± 3.1%. Eighteen plants from Poaceae and one from Cyperaceae supported complete development of the leafhopper. Percent-age survival was highest on maize (93.5%), *Digitaria sanguinalis* (91.8%), *Paspalum paspalodes* (88.6%), and *Ischaemum rugosum* (75.4%). Survival was lowest on wheat (7.0%) and *Cyperus rotundus* (1.0%) (see table). The shortest nymphal duration was recorded on maize (18.6 d), *Echinochloa colona* (20.5 d), and *Eriochloa procera* (21.4 d). The longest duration was on *C. rotundus* (25.0 d). Females laid the most eggs on maize (729/5 females) and the least (0.4-0.7/5 females) on two *Cyperus* spp. Five ovipositional hosts, four Poaceae and one Cyperaceae, failed to support complete insect development. Maize was ranked as the best accepted host as it had the highest nymphal survival and shortest nymphal duration. It was followed by *P. paspalodes* > *D. sanguinalis* > *I. rugosum* > *Paspalidium flavidum*, *C. rotundus* was the least fit host with the lowest survival and longest duration. Nine species—two Poaceae, four Cyperaceae, and three Leguminosae—did not support *C. bipunctata*.

Host plant range of <i>C. bipunctata</i> . IRRRI greenhouse, Jan-May, 1990.				
Host	Parameter			Overall average ranking ^{c/}
	Nymphal survival (%) ^{b/}	Nymphal duration (d) ^{c/}	Eggs laid (no. /5 females)	
Poaceae				
Maize	93.5±4.6a	18.6±2.4a	729.0±344.1a	1
<i>Paspalum paspalodes</i> (= <i>P. distichum</i>)	88.6±13.6ab	22.5±0.7b-e	88.5±41.7b	2
<i>Digitaria sanguinalis</i> (L.) Scop.	91.8±5.2a	24.0±0.5f	82.6±37.2bc	3
<i>Ischaemum rugosum</i> Salisb.	75.4±21.0a-c	23.5±1.1de	44.8±32.5b-d	4
<i>Brachiaria distachya</i> (L.) Stapf.	66.7±42.7b-e	22.6±2.1b-e	29.5±28.7b-d	5
<i>Echinochloa qlabrescens</i> Munro ex Hook f.	66.3±46.3b-e	22.1±0.6b-d	19.9±18.8cd	5
<i>Paspalidium flavidum</i> (Retz.) A. Cameron	71.2±38.2a-d	23.9±1.8ef	66.5±47.5b-d	6
<i>Echinochloa crus-galli</i> (L.) Beauv. ssp. <i>hispidula</i>	54.2±47.2c-f	22.1±0.6bd	19.7±12.1cd	7
<i>E. colona</i> (L.) Link	47.9±22.1d-g	20.5±2.1ab	16.8±10.1d	7
<i>Eriochloa procera</i> (Retz.) C. E. Hubb	49.2±39.6d-g	21.4±2.2ac	20.5±13.1cd	7
<i>Paspalum scrobiculatum</i> L.	64.3±33.9b-e	23.6±5.1ef	26.9±24.2b-d	8
<i>Eleusine indica</i> Gaertn.	43.9±27.8e-g	22.5±1.8b-e	44.8±34.3b-d	9
<i>Panicum repens</i> L.	61.4±34.7c-e	23.7±0.7ef	19.7±18.2cd	10
<i>Brachiaria mutica</i> (Forsk.) Stapf.	45.0±34.0e-g	22.5±0.9b-e	11.7±9.9d	11
<i>Leptochloa chinensis</i> (L.) Nees	26.2±14.6gh	23.6±1.7ef	2.4±1.9d	12
Rice TN1 variety	30.2±25.4f-h	24.0±0.5f	15.3±13.6d	12
<i>Imperata cylindrica</i> (L.) Beauv.	8.0±4.2hi	23.5±1.3de	3.4±2.4d	13
Wheat	7.0±4.8hi	23.1±1.1de	3.0±1.2d	13
<i>Cynodon dactylon</i> (L.) Pers. ^{e/}	0i	0h	8.5±7.7d	15
<i>Chloris barbata</i> Sw. ^{e/}	0i	0h	7.6±4.7d	15
<i>Paspalum conjugatum</i> Berg. ^{e/}	0i	0h	2.2±2.0d	15
<i>Leersia hexandra</i> Sw. Retz Honda ^{e/}	0i	0h	1.0±0.8d	15
Cyperaceae				
<i>Cyperus rotundus</i> L.	0±0.8i	25.0±0q	0.7±0.5d	14
<i>C. difformis</i> L. ^{e/}	0i	0h	0.4±0.2d	15

^{a/} Av of 10 replications. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different (P < 0.01) by LSD statistical test. Nymphs did not survive and eggs were not laid on *Sorghum halepense* (L.) Pers. and *Isachne globosa* (Thund.) O. K. In the Poaceae family; on *C. brevifolius* (Rottb.) Hassk., *C. iria* L., *C. diffusa* L., and *Fimbristylis miliacea* L. In the Cyperaceae family; and on soybean, mungbean, and cowpea in the Leguminosae family.

^{b/} Survival (%) = [Nymphs becoming adults (no.) / Initial nymphs (no.)] × 100.

^{c/} n = 10 ^{d/} 1 = most suitable, 15 = least suitable. ^{e/} No nymphs survived.

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